

Selawa.

A few hundred yards from the rock temple at Selawa, upon a low outcrop of rock, within a tract of paddy fields, are vestiges of a long inscription in the character of the tenth century, best known by the example on the basement course of the building at the head of the broad stairway at Mihintalé.

The inscription is too weather-worn to admit of anything but a fragmentary copy being made.¹ It may be assigned to Kassapa V., or his son-in-law Kassapa VI. (931-41 or 954-64 A.D.).

Wattarama.

Two pillars (one broken) within the temple premises, placed near the steps to the present viháré, bear inscriptions, separated by lines. A word or two may be made out here and there with difficulty, but otherwise the writing is hopelessly illegible. The form of Sinhalese character proves it to be of this period.²

Pillar (i.), 12 in. by 8 in.; inscribed on three sides; A, 12 lines apparent; B, 21 lines; C, 19; on the upper part letters quite effaced.

Pillar (ii.), 12 in. by 8 in.; broken in two; inscribed on all four faces. A, 24 lines; B, 49; C, 39; D, 23; letters a little larger and somewhat more modern than those on (i.).

Belonging to these centuries, two portions of inscribed pillars, extremely weathered,³ were found, the one at **Diyasumata**, Međamędiliya Pattuwa, Kinigođa Kóralé, the other at **Erabadapela**, Međa Pattuwa, Galbođa Kóralé.

TWELFTH AND THIRTEENTH CENTURIES.

Dewanagala.

No. 1.

Parákrama Báhu I.

This inscription is cut on the slope of the rock beside the longer ascent to the summit of the hill, and about a quarter of a mile off the minor road from Máwanella to Alpitíya.

It covers a surface of 9 ft. by 8 ft. 9 in., and comprises 22 lines, of which the last three are pushed out to the left some 18 in. owing to the unevenness of the rock on the right. Below are engraved the sun and moon symbols. The first seven or eight lines are deeply incised in letters 3 to 4 in. broad—evidently the re-chiselling of a later period, and not improbably the handiwork of the mason who cut the more modern inscription on the summit of Dewanagala and executed the carving of the adjacent *Srī patula*.¹ The greater part of the inscription is barely legible, and only in the morning so long as the sun casts a shadow, before it rises high above the hill.²

Dr. Müller has not been fortunate in his treatment of this fine inscription. Misled by the form of introduction, he classes it among those of the eleventh century, and dismisses it with a scant notice bristling with inaccuracies:—

Dewanagala, Galboda Korle, Mađa Pattu, three miles from Máwanella resthouse, on the road to Aelpitíya (Kégalla District, Western Province). The temple is on the top of an immense rock to which steps lead; the inscription is at the bottom of the rock, about a quarter mile off the road in the jungle. Five lines are only preserved, which contain the usual introduction of the inscription of the eleventh century (see for instance Mayilagstota, Ambasthala), but unfortunately not the name of the king; the greater part of the inscription is completely effaced.

Sirivat apiriyat lo ikat gura mulin utavat iru Damba (2) divuhi an kaet kula paemili kaja Okawas parapuren bat (3) kela usabnat ayanchesari wa Lak dimu poloyogen parapuren himi (4) tumá sarana tisara sin gal raja madum wisasawá sáha tedin hira (5) paŕa belin mehesu ratol áewin dawuwa raja wiru

The glorious endless, whose renown extended over the whole world, who was an object of veneration to the other royal dynasties of Dambadiwa, descended from the uninterrupted line of the Ikshwáku family, an eminent Kshatriya, born in the womb of the chief queen, who had become lord of Laŕká by (hereditary) succession.³

Apart from its palaeographic value, the inscription is of exceptional historical interest from containing reference to warlike events in the reign of the most famous of Sinhalese kings. In this respect it offers a pleasing contrast to the long inscription of the same monarch at the Galviháré, Polonnaruwa. His struggle for the supremacy with Gaja Báhu II. and Mánábharaņa, and the account of the expedition against Aramaņa (Rámañña), related in detail in the "Maháwaņasa," find striking confirmation in this rock-cut grant to one of his great generals. It further furnishes a satisfactory adjustment in the date of Parákrama Báhu's accession as *Chakravartti* ruler over the entire "Tri Siphala" (Pihiti, Máya, Rnhaņa), and the sequence of the Burmese war.

Assuming (with the "Maháwaņasa" editors) 1120 A.D. to be the correct date of the decease of Vijaya Báhu I., Parákrama Báhu commenced his pseudo "holy war," on the authority of this contemporary record, in 1162 A.D., when "the Buddhist religion had suffered decline for forty-two years since the death of his grandfather Vijaya Rája." The stubborn Mánábharaņa held his own for some time,⁴ and it is reasonable to infer that Parákrama Báhu was not crowned Overlord of all Ceylon, for the second time, until 1164 A.D.⁵

The relation of the Aramaņa expedition in the "Maháwaņasa" immediately follows the revolt at Mántota (Mahátittba) of the 16th year of Parákrama Báhu's reign. This has naturally led Turnour

¹ A photograph was taken, but during rain, as time pressed. A careful examination of the inscription in fine weather might perhaps fix the name of the royal grantor.

² "A peculiar Sinhalese character did not originate until the eighth or ninth century." (Müller, *loc. cit.*, Introd.) Rather it should be said that the gradual transition from the old angular type had then developed the main features of that rounded form, which only acquired its modern graceful shape after the lapse of a further period of six or seven centuries.

³ Both now at Kégalla.

⁴ The stone-mason, of Imbulgođa in Uđapala Kóralé, has left this record on the rock near the viháré:—*Uđapala Kóralé Imbulgođa gal vađu nođe me viharaye galvalaval kofa galharu strukotayá.*

⁵ The accompanying lithograph is from a photograph of an impression of the first seven lines—the only portion capable of being reproduced.

⁶ Müller, *loc. cit.*, pp. 60, 87, 120.

⁷ The virulence of the old chronicler against this valiant prince, no lover of the priesthood, finds vent in the closing words of the scene at Mánábharaņa's deathbed. "And when he had spoken these words he wept bitterly, and, as if it moved him to go unto the place whither the good soldiers of the great king Parákrama would not desire to follow him, he set out for the fortress of the Ruler of Hell." (Maháwaņasa, Chap. LXXII. 342, English translation, p. 190.)

⁸ The date adopted by the editors of the "Maháwaņasa." Turnour ("Epitome of the History of Ceylon," Ceylon Almanac, 1833, p. 253), perhaps following the "Nikáya Sangrahawa," throws back the commencement of Parákrama Báhu's reign eleven years, viz., to 1696 A.B. = 1153 A.D.

to place both in the same year.¹ The inscription fixes the foreign war as falling between that rising and the Ruhuna rebellion of the 8th year, by allotting it to the 12th year of his rule, *v. e.*, 1176 A.D. This date is collaterally confirmed by the name of the Aramaña ruler given in the inscription. The "ruler styled Bhuvanāditta" can be no other than Narabāditsi-tsi-thu,² the Pugañ (Burmese) King, who reigned between 1167-1204³ A.D.

The perfidy and lawless acts of "the King of Rāmañña," the forbearance of Parākrama Báhu under repeated indignities, his ultimate wrath, and stern requital, are graphically set forth in the "Mahāwaṅsa." On the other hand, the annals of Burma observe a discreet and significant silence touching the events.

Now, because that the inhabitants of Laṅkā and Rāmañña professed the same true faith, there never was any difference between them. The lords of the island of Laṅkā and the rulers of the country of Rāmañña were alike exceeding zealous followers of the Blessed One. Wherefore many kings of old who reigned in the two countries had a great regard one to another, and lived as true friends. They sent rich gifts to each other in great number, and preserved their friendship for a long time without breach. And the king of Rāmañña, like the kings that went before him, continued the ancient friendship with king Parākrama Báhu also. But at one time this foolish king hearkened to the words of certain messengers who went from this country, and uttered slanders in his ears; and thereafter he ceased to furnish the ambassadors of the king of Laṅkā who were at his court with the expenses that were given to them aforesaid according to custom. And he also made a decree that the elephants that many persons had sold in his kingdom for export should not any longer be sold. Moreover, with evil intent, the king also set a high price on the beasts, commanding that the elephants which were sold in former times for a hundred *ukkhallas* of silver, or a thousand, should now be sold for two thousand or three thousand. And he likewise put an end to the ancient custom of giving an elephant to every ship that bore presents to the king. Even when the messengers of the king of Laṅkā brought him letters written on leaves of gold, he robbed them of all their treasure, and imprisoned them in a fortress in the hill country, pretending that they were sent to Kamboja, or saying something of that sort. And notwithstanding that he had heard how the king of Laṅkā had shown kindness to his ambassador Tapassi, this unjust king deprived the messengers of the chief of Laṅkā of their wealth and their elephants and their ships and all that pertained to them. And he caused their feet to be beaten with sticks, and employed them to draw water in prisons. And on one occasion, when a certain chief of India, Kassapa by name, sent presents unto him of great value with a letter written on a leaf of gold, he hindered the men who bore them from landing, and then caused the presents to be taken from them with the letter and sent into the city with great dishonour. And after that he sent one day unto the Sinhalese ambassadors, saying: "Henceforth shall ye not send ships from the Sinhalese country into our country; and if the chiefs of the Sinhalese do so, then should not any man blame us if we put the messengers to death that come hither. (Give us now, therefore, a writing, saying that ye have received intimation hereof; else ye shall surely not be permitted to return to your homes." And when he had thus put them in fear and had made them a promise that he would allow them to return to their own country, he caused them to put it in writing, and took the paper from their hands. And he commanded Vāgissara the scholar and Dhammakitti the pandit to be sent on the open sea in a ship that leaked (and was not sound).

On a certain other occasion also he took the presents and the merchandise from the messengers whom the lord of Laṅkā had sent in charge thereof that they might buy elephants, saying, "Fourteen elephants shall we give you or their value in money." But he spake only a lie, and gave nothing unto them. Afterwards again he violently seized a princess that the lord of Laṅkā had sent to the country of Kamboja.

And when the king Parākrama Báhu heard of the many wrongs that were oftentimes done unto him by the king of Rāmañña, he waxed exceeding wrath, and said: "What king is there in the whole of India that dare behave to my ambassadors in this manner?" And he sent unto his ministers, saying, "It seemeth necessary that we should now compass the king Arimaddana (Arimardana) to take him captive or to kill him."

Thereupon a certain Tamil commander of high rank in the army, Adicca (Aditya) by name stood up with his hands raised to his forehead. And as he was desirous to go to war he spake these words unto the king, saying: "O king! let not the chief ministers of the kingdom be employed in this work. Let the command be given unto me, and I shall in no wise transgress the bounds of the king's orders. And surely it is not a hard thing even for me alone to carry out successfully the wishes of my lord the king, whose commands no man can set at naught."

And when the king had hearkened unto him he was greatly pleased, and set all the captains that were fit for the enterprise under him, and commanded him to depart quickly.

Then the great king commanded that they should make ready many hundred ships of divers kinds, and that there should be no delay. And all the country round about the coast seemed like one great workshop busied with the constant building of ships. And the building of all those ships was finished in five months; and he gathered them together with all speed at the port Pallava-vaṅka. And then the king, in his great majesty, supplied them to the full with all things that were necessary for the enterprise, namely, rice and other provisions for the voyage, that would last for one year; armour, weapons, and the like; hundreds and thousands of coats wrought of iron and skins of deer, to keep the sharp-pointed arrows from piercing them; divers kinds of medicines filled in the horns of bullocks as a balm to the burning wounds caused by poisoned arrows; drugs of divers kinds also to serve as antidotes if they should chance to drink of the poisoned waters of divers streams; pincers of iron for drawing out the arrows with poisoned tips that, by reason of their having entered deep into the flesh, could not be drawn out (by the hand); and likewise, physicians of great skill, and nurses also. And the king, whom no one could equal in ordering things aright, sent on board a mighty army numbering many thousands; and sent out, in one day, all those ships laden with good soldiers and much provision, so that the fleet of ships that conveyed the great army seemed like an island moving in the midst of the sea.

But because of the stormy weather certain of these ships were wrecked, and certain others were driven on strange lands. And many soldiers of great skill who had embarked in one of the ships landed at Kākādīpa, and fought a battle there, and carried many of the inhabitants captive, and brought them away in safety, and took them before the king of Laṅkā.

But five of the ships that carried a great host of strong men landed at the port Kusimi in the country of Rāmañña. And these valiant soldiers were led by Kittī and Nagaragiri; and, being provided with weapons and armour, they advanced from the port where they landed and fought many fierce battles and slew many thousands of the forces of the Rāmañña country. Like furious elephants they destroyed a great number of coconut and other trees in the places round about them, and burned many villages with fire, and destroyed half of the kingdom.

And the ship which the Tamil General Adicca commanded cast anchor at the port Papphāla in that country. And these men also, led by the Tamil commander, began straightway a fierce and bloody war, and took many of the inhabitants captive, and shook the kingdom of Rāmañña greatly. And after this the mighty and terrible Sinhalese entered the city, and spared not their weapons, and slew the King of Rāmañña who had disregarded the laws of nations.⁴ And when they had subdued the inhabitants of Rāmañña and conquered the kingdom, these great warriors

¹ Turnour, *loc. cit.* In the "Narēndracharitāvalokana-pradīpikāśva," the account of the Burmese war is given directly after the Ruhuna revolt.

² *Bhuvana* = "world"; *Naraba* = Sans. *nara-bhū*, "land of man"; *Aditta*; *Aditsi-tsi* = Pāli *ādichcha*, "sun." Both names therefore mean "sun of the world." According to the Burmese "Sāsana-waṅsa," the capital of Burma during this period was "Arimaddanapura in Rāmañña"; and hence the Burmese king is called in the "Mahāwaṅsa" "Arimaddana rājās" (Pāli); *Arimaddana rājās* (Sip.) a metonymic substitution of the name of the city for that of its ruler (cf. *Kōṭṭē rājās*). *Arimaddanapura*, "the city (pura) ruled by the Ari priests," the hierophants of the Nāga or dragon-worship, formerly prevalent in Burma.

³ See Sir A. P. Phayre's "History of Burma," 1868, pp. 50, 231, 239. Rāmañña or Pega was subject to Burma from 1050 to 1290 A.D. approximately.

rode on the noble white elephant and marched round the city without fear, and afterward, proclaimed, by the beating of drums, the supreme authority of the lord of Lanġá (over that kingdom).

Then the people of Rāmañña trembled with fear (for the safety of their country), and seeing none other means of escape (from their troubles) they assembled themselves and took counsel together. And they sent messengers with letters to the order of priests that dwelt in the Island of Lanġá, saying, "Take henceforth from us, as a yearly tribute, as many elephants as are necessary. We are deserving of compassion at your merciful and divine hands, who, by speaking words of counsel, can turn the King of Lanġá from his purpose, that so he may not thus cruelly lay waste our possessions." And the King's heart was made soft towards them by the words that the priests of the three brotherhoods spake unto him; and the people of Rāmañña sent yearly many elephants, and entered again into a covenant with the lord of Lanġá, and made him a true friend.¹

Text.

1. සිරිවින්² අසිරිවින්³ ලොවුණුකුන් ගුණ මුළුකුකුරන් මුළුදඩ
2. දිවිහි අන් කැන්කුල පැමිලිකල ඛනාවස් රජපරපුරන් බව
3. කැන්මසබනව අගමෙලෙසුන්වු ලක්දිවු පොලොයොහොන් පරපුරෙන් හිමි
4. තුමා සරණනිසරසිත් අන්රජ මුදුන්සෙසවු සාහ⁴ ගෙදින් ඡරා
5. පැලකෙවින්⁵ මෙහෙසුරු දලදපින් උච්ඡු⁶ රජවිතින් සුරිඡු⁷ පබඡු⁸ දෙගෙන් දි
6. හිසුරු සන්සෙතින් කිතිසර පැනසරින් සුරගුරු සොඡුගුණෙන් නිස
7. සුර රුසරින්⁹ කදව්¹⁰ කුලඡුසරින් බොහොසත් දිඡු සහ වොවුකු රජබ
8. රණ කිරණ වුදුරුදු වුලසල අරිකුණකුකු කපකුර මෙන් නොමිත් නන්
9. රුවන් සහ වතුරෙන් නන්දෙසෙන් ඔසල මුළුදිඡු සින්සසුර පුරමින්
10. මුළුලොහි පනල සැස පමනඡු¹¹ ඇති රුසුරජකුකු කුමා විදනලයෙහි¹² සි
11. හ පරකුම ඇති පරකුමබාහු වන්හිමිසන්වහන්සේ නමන් මු
12. කුන් මිස්සරණසා සබ්බසන්හ¹³ නැනැ සිටැ දෙසැලිස් හවු
13. රුදුන් නැව්වුකු ලොසසුන් ඇතිකරවමි සන සිතින් ගපබාහු
14. [මානාවරණ]දෙදෙහා¹⁴ සුඡාකොට ලංකාවිසමෙහි එකවිටකොට¹⁵
15. පැ (ඡුඡුබඡු) රහිර අඡු වලඡුන¹⁶ සමාහි දෙලොසවන පොසොන්පුර දස
16. වකැ අරමණ (වසන) හුමනාදිත්ත නන් කෙතනකුන් රජකරන¹⁷ කලැ ලක්දිවු
17. සන්තාන බොකරමහස් කියා හටන්නැවු දහස්තනන්කොට පිරිස් නහා
18. යව් අපමණස පාලෙන් පදල කලකින් (උඡු සමින්) කුසුම්සොසි සන නුවරක්
19. පැහැරු පස්මසක් (රජ හේවාගත්) කලැ අර[මණ]සන් සන්තාන කරවිහසි දුතස
20. න් (එවුණෙස) කිත්කුමරගි[රි]න්ම හිරසදපවන්තාමෙන් සිරිතා පරිඡෙ
21. න් (මුත්ව දුන ම)ලබවු හා පෙර (. . හ) නිත්සෙන්පවයෙ
22. න් කිඡුචට දෙලොසමුඡු දෙපැලක් ඇතුළුවැ දෙයාලක් පමුඡුකොටැ දුන්තෙසි

Transcript.

1. Sīriwat apiriwat levu ikut guṇa muḥinurat muḥu Damba
2. dīvīhi an keṭ kula pemili kaḷa Okkāsā rada parapuren bāta
3. keṭ osabanāṭa agamehesunvū Lagdivu poḷoyohon parapuren himi
4. tumā sarāṇa niya reṣin an rāja mudun bisēsvū sāha tedin Hiru
5. peḷakevin Mehesuru daḷadeḷin Uvindu rāja viritin Surindu pabānda denen Di
6. nisuru sat setin Kitisara peusarin Suraguru somu guṇen Nisa
7. yuru rusarin Kaṇḍav kulupu sarin Bohosāt dinū saha voṭunu rāja ba
8. rāṇa kirāṇa vuduruḍu tala kala aritu itunu kapṭu amen nomiu nan
9. ruvan yāna vaturen nan desen oṣāḷa muḥu diḷindu siṭṭayura puramin
10. muḥu lohi pataḷa yeṣa pambānda eṭi ruḷu rajātunṅga kumba vidanalayehi sī
11. ha parākrama eṭi Parākrama Bāhu vat himiyanvahansē taman mu
12. tun Vijaya Rājapī swarggasthāṅgya teṇe siṭṭe desālis havu
13. ruddak neṣi tubū losasan eṭikarawami yāna siṭin Gaḷa Bāhu
14. [Mānābharaṇa] dedehā yuddha koṭa Lanġādvīpāyehi ekachchātra koṭa
15. pe (muṇu bandu) Raṅgira āsri walandana samāhi doḷoswana Poson pura dasa
16. wake Aramaṇa (wasana) Bhuvandāḷitta nan kenekun rajakarana kalē Lakdivu
17. santāna nokarambhayī kiyaḷ haṭan nevu dahasganan koṭa piriṣ naṅgā
18. yawḷa Aramaṇuṇu pāren padaḷa kalakin (uhu yamin) Kusumiyā yeṇi yāna nuwarak
19. peḷeṇe pasmasak (rāja hēvāgan) kalē Ara [maṇa] yān santāna karawamāyī dūtaya
20. n (evuhēya) Kinnuwaragi [ri] nṭa hiraṣāṇḍa pawatnāteḷ siṭinā paridde
21. n (munṭa duna Ma) labāṭuwa hā Pera (. . ha) niṣenpawaye
22. n bijuwaṭa doḷosamuṇu deḷelak eṭuḷuḷe deṇṅalāk pamuṇu koṭe dunnēyi.

Translation.

The illustrious monarch, Parākrama Bāhu, lord of wealth, abounding in virtuous qualities pre-eminent in the boundless world; lineally descended from the royal Okkāka dynasty, who threw into shade the other Kshatriya races of the whole of Dambādīva; [ruler] by hereditary descent of the territory of the Island of Lanġā, chief queen unto the Kshātrya nobility; [this king] who has anointed other kings with the effulgence of the nails of his feet; who in glory has surpassed the Sun god; in prowess, Maheswara (Siva); in haughty spirit, Vishnu; in kingly state, Sakra; in inexhaustible wealth, Kuvēra; in [bestowing] happiness, Kitisara; in profound wisdom, Vrihaspati; in gentleness, the Moon; in the grace of his beauty, Kandarpa; in richness of benevolence, the Bōdhisat; who glitters in the resplendence of his crown and royal apparel; who has acquired world-wide fame unbroken, by filling the ocean of the hearts of all poor men who flock from various countries with the water of manifold gems, like a wish-conferring tree to those of righteous intent; who displays to hostile kings the strength of a lion in cleaving the frontal globe of the forehead of elephants; [this king] intending to promote the Buddhist religion and the interests of the people, which had been neglected for forty-two years since the death of his grandfather, king Wijaya [Bāhu], made war with the two [princes] Gaḷa Bāhu [and Mānābharaṇa] and brought Lanġā under one canopy of dominion. Whilst in the enjoyment of blessings as [high] as Swarnagiri thereby received, in the 12th year [of his reign] on the 10th day of the waxing moon of [the month] Poson [the king] saying "We do not hold Lanġā in peace so long as a personage by name Bhuvandāḷitta dwelling in Aramaṇa rules there,"¹⁷ prepared and manned thousands of warships and despatched

¹ Mahawamsa, Chap. LX XVI, 10-75 (English translation, pp. 229-232).
² සිරිවින් ³ අසිරිවින් ⁴ සාහ ⁵ පැලකෙවින් ⁶ උච්ඡු ⁷ සුරිඡු ⁸ පබඡු ⁹ රුසරින් ¹⁰ කදව් ¹¹ සබඡු
¹² කුමරා විදනලයෙහි ¹³ සබ්බසා ¹⁴ දෙදෙහා ¹⁵ එකවිටකු ¹⁶ වලඡුන ¹⁷ රජකරණ
¹⁷ Aramaṇa, Rāmañña, or Rāmaṇya, was the country within the delta of the Irāvādī, better known later as Pegu, from the name of its capital, formerly Hapsāwādī.

them. They steered a course for (*lit.* rowed by way of) Aramaña, and reaching there in course of time took by storm a town called Kusumiya,¹ and continued the war for five months.² Then messengers were sent [to them] with the order "Do ye make peace with the people of *Uvamaña*." To Kit-nuwara-giri³ (Kirtti-nagara-giri) was granted as *paravenu* lands to be held so long as sun and moon endure..... [the village] Malabaṭṭawa and.....² *yālu* 12 *umayū* and 2 *pēlas* of paddy sowing extent to be held without molestation.

Eyungalla.

In the Māvata Pattuwa of the Paranakūru Kóralé. Three inscriptions identical in text, differing only in the size of the letters, their number in each line and the position of the sun and moon, &c., cut with them.

No. 1: on one side of a small slab 2 ft. 2 in. by 2 ft. by 5½ in. found at the foot of a *bulu* tree (*Terminalia bellerica*) in a chena, half a mile from the Rāja Maha Viháre at Kavudugma. Moon and sun to right of letters.

No. 2: on a rock two feet under the mud of a paddy field. This has sun and moon above and a crow at the end; the writing covers 2 ft. by 1 ft. 6 in.

No. 3: cut on a low flat hump of rock, the boundary limit between Eyungalla and Dívela. A sun and a moon engraved below. The letters are large and shallow, and either wilfully or from carelessness have been injured by fire.

It is probable that a fourth stone, similarly inscribed, existed somewhere in the neighbourhood, completing the boundaries of the extent of land gifted to the *pirivena* :—

This *pirivena* at Eyungalla may have been one of the monasteries established by "the pious and wise" Mahindu, minister of Parákrama Báhu I., of whom it is recorded in the "Maháwaṅsa" :—

And it so happened that among the ministers of the inner palace of this king, who was like unto Meru amidst all the races of kings that were like mountains, there was a pious and wise man, Mahinda by name, who loved the Three Gems with all his heart,—a man pure in heart and of sound wisdom, and one who knew what was good and evil, and had a knowledge of the ways and methods and forms and practices for doing religious works, without being moved either by love or hate, or by fear or ignorance. And though he had heaped up much merit, yet was he not satisfied therewith, being like unto the ocean that the waters never satisfy. And he abstained from sin by reason of the shame and fear within him, and strove always to overcome difficulties. And for a recompense for the noble foothold that was made holy by reason of its being washed with the nectar of the four and eighty thousand sections of the law (delivered by the Buddha and his disciples), he, with the favour of the gracious king, who always gave help to good works, caused a wonderful temple of great splendour to be built, giving delight to all.⁴

No. 1.

<i>Text.</i>	<i>Transcript.</i>
1. ආභුණුග	1. Ehuṅuga
2. ල මහෙසු	2. Ila Mahendra
3. ලංකා දිකිතා)	3. Lanṭā Adhikā
4. ර පිටිවනු කු ○	4. va Pirivena ku
5. සලානයි	5. salānaya

No. 2.

1. ආභුණුගලල	1. Ehuṅugalla
2. මහෙසු ලංකා ද	2. Mahendra Lanṭā A
3. ධිකිතා පිටිවනු	3. dhikāra Pirivena
4. කුසලානයි	4. kusalānaya

No. 3.

1. [ආභු] භුණුලල	1. [Ehu] ṅugalla
2. මහෙසු ලං	2. Mahendra Lanṭ
3. කා[ආ]ධිකිතා පි	3. kā [A]dhikāra Pi
4. පිටිවනු කුසලානයි	4. rivena kusalānaya

Translation.

The benefaction made to Mahendara Lanṭā Adhikāra Pirivena at Ehuṅugalla.

Ganegoda.

On the soffit of a fallen lintel—part of the stone remains of the old viháre—is carved in modern characters, but dated Saka 1103 (= 1181 A.D.), a short spurious grant to "the viháre in Ganegoda village, bounded on the east by Yakgala, west by the éla, south by Panṅgala, north by Puwalgolla and the éla." This clumsy forgery is said to have been the work of a resident priest not many years ago.

¹ *Kusumi*. Not improbably Thahtun, the native name for the ancient capital of Pegu, which in the Mun language signifies "golden land," the legendary *Suvarnu Bhami*. It lies on a tidal creek opening into the gulf of Martaban (Phayre, *loc. cit.*, pp. 21-28). *Kusumiya*, if derived from *kusumba*, "gold," would be a natural Sighalese translation. The Sighalese advanced inland, and "entered the city" (Maháwaṅsa, l. c.). The Páli text (l.) reads "*nagaraṅ vikkamaṅ*"; the "Naréndra-charitávalokana-pradípikáwa." (ii) "*Ukka nam nuvara*"; the Sighalese version of the "Maháwaṅsa." (iii) *krama ullatighavaya kala nuvara*." If the simpler rendering of (i.) and (ii.) be adopted, by "the city Ukka," the capital of Rámañña, Bogo or Pegu, might well be meant. In that case the captured "King" would in all probability be a viceroy of Narabaditsthu, the Burmese king, then resident at Pugán, far up the Iráwádi.

² During the thirty-seven years reign of Narabaditsthu "there was constant communication with Ceylon, from whence came four great Ráhan, who introduced some new philosophical or religious doctrines; but no change in worship was made." (Phayre, *loc. cit.*, p. 50.) Among the four seem to have been those famous scholars of the day, Wagávara, and Dharmakírtti, whose treatment by the Arimaddana ruler, when ambassadors, helped to fill up the measure of the wrath of Parákrama Báhu. The Burmese "Sásanawaṅsaya" records that Páli scholars from Ceylon visited Arimaddanapura, the capital of Rámañña, during this reign.

³ *Kirttinagaragiri* (Sip. recenscion), *Kirttipuravava* "Naréndracharitávalokana-pradípikáwa.") The combined names would seem to apply to a single commander.

⁴ Since sent to the Colombo Museum. The lithograph is from a photograph.

⁵ Maháwaṅsa, Chap. LXXIII., 124-129 (English translation, p. 200).